

COGNITIVE ACTIVITY APPROACH IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15029697>

Abstract. *The article discusses some aspects of the development and implementation of a cognitive activity approach in the professional training of future teachers. This approach is aimed at developing the student's personality based on the development of universal ways of activity. The personality of the student becomes a systemic component of the professional training of future teachers based on the cognitive activity approach. The cognitive-activity approach allows us to move from the reproductive method of learning to the activity paradigm, in which the key competence is the presence of a person's foundations of theoretical thinking, capable of finding non-standard solutions in uncertain conditions and acting in uncertain situations.*

Keywords: *cognitive-activity approach, values, meanings, the principle of value-semantic orientation, cognitive-value mechanism of self-regulation of life.*

At the present stage, the main goal of professional training is the development of student competencies capable of successful self-determination, continuous self-education, self-regulation in professional and socio-cultural activities. In this case, knowledge as a value is transformed from the dominant goal of vocational education into a means of personal development. The personality of the student becomes a systemic component of the cognitive modeling of the professional training of future teachers based on the cognitive activity approach. It provides the content of the main professional educational program) in terms of didactics with such competencies as:

- the ability to model the educational process using modern technologies;
- knowledge of the methods of project and innovation activities in educational and upcoming professional activities;
- realization of oneself as a person with a basic level of competence based on the integration of knowledge, skills, skills, experience of cultural, social, professional mobility in accordance with personal needs and requirements of employers (professional standard);
- the strategic goal of the development of cognitive modeling cognition in educational and professional activities is a form of assistance to students in educational and professional activities, which determines support and correction in building a student's professional and semantic system and involves the organization of three-way communications: “teacher -student - educational space”.

It is this aspect that is important from the point of view of cognitive pedagogy and is used in the development of theoretical, methodological and methodological levels of providing cognitive modeling in the process of professional training of future teachers based on a cognitive activity approach, and although various technologies are implemented in pedagogy in order to improve the learning and upbringing process, both practitioners and researchers do not pay enough attention the properties and features of the tools that a person uses in the process of cognition.

In research on pedagogy, it is stated as a well-known fact that people differ in the properties of their cognitive organization, which determines the results of their activities. However, as the analysis of existing pedagogical research shows, for teachers, the process of cognition based on the cognitive organization of each student is poorly controlled.

In the activity of teachers, it is assumed that there is a natural process of maturation of the cognitive organization of a person's personality, which develops on the basis of interaction between the teacher and the student within the educational environment.

Thus, we state that in pedagogical science and practice insufficient attention is paid to the quality of the cognitive tool used by a person, and we believe that the creation of an instrumental sphere of the educational environment conducive to the development of an effective cognitive organization of the student, equipping it with universal tools, both internal and external, to solve his life and professional problems is the main the task of the modern pedagogical process.

It is the cognitive activity approach, as a methodological basis, that defines the instrumental sphere of the educational environment, which means not only the physical and social factors of learning and upbringing, but also the internal activity of students, generating meta-tools and ways to solve problems.

The cognitive activity approach determines:

- formation of a person's readiness for self-development and continuous education based on learned values and meanings;
- design and construction of a holistic personality-developing educational environment;
- active value-semantic educational and cognitive activity, taking into account individual characteristics;
- the development of cognitive-value mechanisms of regulation of effective behavior of the student.

The cognitive-activity approach allows you to get away from the reproductive way of learning and move on to the activity paradigm, in which the key competence is the presence of the basics of theoretical thinking in the student, who is able to find an adequate solution in non-standard conditions and act in uncertain situations; to model the subject content aimed at finding generalized ways of action by building a system of scientific concepts.

This approach is aimed at developing the personality of the student on the basis of mastering and developing universal ways of activity. The main pedagogical task is to create conditions that initiate the action of students: updating the value content of education - the assimilation of knowledge as a value of learning - the implementation of modern interactive and information and communication technologies of education.

The cognitive activity approach can be used at all levels of education according to the algorithm:

- defining the value-semantic goals of education in the form of a system of key tasks reflecting the main directions of the formation of professionally significant personal qualities of a student and the development of her cognitive organization;
- modeling of methods of action based on constructed value-semantic goals, ensuring interdisciplinary integration of the value-semantic content of learning; highlighting the main results of the educational process as achievements of personal, socio-cultural, communicative, cognitive development of students.

We have established that the cognitive-activity approach is able to overcome the crisis of value perception of education and is focused on the development of the student's personality, its

cognitive organization, the development of values and meanings, which are, in fact, a regulator of human activity (cognitive-value mechanism of self-regulation of behavior). The student solves certain tasks with the help of various cognitive tools, which include not only “external”, but also “internal” tools presented in the form of information processing and transformation structures (intelligence, cognitive styles, memory, attention, etc.). Traditionally, it is stated that people differ in the properties of their cognitive organization (mind, intellect, abilities), which manifests itself in different results of cognition. The tools by which the process of cognition is carried out, the acquisition of new knowledge about the world around us, are the methods of cognition (empirical and theoretical).

As an internal tool of cognition and the result of thought processes, the intellect is considered, combining all the cognitive abilities of an individual: sensation, perception, memory, representation, thinking, imagination. External tools of cognition are various means designed to organize and facilitate the process of cognition, which include information and educational technologies that support, direct and expand the thought processes of their users and contribute to the activation and intensification of students’ activities.

It is important for future teachers to master the methods of situational analysis and management of developments in crisis environments and non-standard situations based on a cognitive activity approach in the following stages:

1. Conducting information monitoring of socio-economic situations.
2. Development of a methodology for analyzing problematic situations.
3. Development of analytical scenarios for the development of problematic situations and their management.
4. Preparation of recommendations for solving priority educational problems based on the results of the analysis of problematic situations.
5. Monitoring of problematic situations in the development of education in the region, municipality, educational organization, study group, at the level of each student.
6. Definition of the technology of cognitive modeling of purposeful value-semantic development of all subjects of the educational process.
7. Development of a model for the formation of methods of regulation and self-regulation of cognitive processes by subjects of educational activity.

The theoretical and methodological basis of cognitive modeling consists of systemic and functional patterns that constitute the essence of the cognitive activity approach to the professional training of future teachers.

Systemic patterns:

- the effectiveness of professional training of future teachers within the framework of the activity paradigm of education is achieved by observing the consistent integration of education, science and the labor market in accordance with the profile orientation;
- the formation and development of universal, general cultural and professional competencies of students in the process of professional training takes place on the basis of acquired knowledge, skills and abilities; values and meanings;
- the value-semantic potential of a student's professional training is realized in the conditions of a personal-developing environment of an educational organization;
- the implementation of the universal competencies of the future teacher is provided by the formed personally and professionally significant qualities, in accordance with the specialty.

Functional patterns:

- increasing the level of implementation of universal competencies of future teachers effectively on the basis of a cognitive-activity approach within the framework of the activity paradigm of education;

- selection and structuring of educational material, the choice of teaching methods is carried out while maintaining the integrity of the value-semantic basis of fundamental, interdisciplinary support;

- students' qualitative assimilation of the content of academic disciplines is carried out on the basis of value-semantic modular design of educational material.

The established systemic and functional patterns determine the principles of the cognitive activity approach corresponding to them:

- motivational and creative activity of the student (formation of positive motivational structures and attitudes in educational and creative activities);

- interdisciplinary integration (thematic and targeted integration of the content of academic disciplines);

- diagnostic goal setting (the relationship of goal setting with probabilistic consequences);

- value-semantic orientation (self-regulation of behavior based on values and meanings).

The professional training of future teachers contains a set of prerequisites and organizational and pedagogical conditions, which were the result of a search for internal trends in its functioning and development. It acts as a functional unity of the processes of goal-setting, mastering the content of education based on modern educational technologies, interaction of participants in the educational process (formal and informal, guided and acting in forms of self-education and self-development), conducting external and internal evaluation of learning outcomes based on the values and meanings of education.

The system of professional training of future teachers, designed in line with the cognitive-activity approach as a methodological basis within the framework of the activity paradigm of education, contains the following structural components: target (motivational-value), meaningful, technological, activity-based, reflexive-evaluative.

The initial link in the implementation of the cognitive-activity approach is the setting of professional training goals, which should reflect modern requirements for a teacher as a person and a professional and contribute to increasing motivation and developing value-semantic orientations of students that meet both the requirements of society and their own self-development, self-realization in future teaching activities [3;4;7].

The content component reveals the features of building the content of the implementation of the system of professional training of future teachers in stages: understanding the system of educational goals in the context of value-semantic orientation and profile of professional training; data analysis for the formation of the program;

- development of the general concept of the educational program; building a model of the value and semantic orientations of the graduate; creation of a software package of the educational program;

- creating a subject-based personal development environment, clarifying the structure and ways of presenting the content of education at the cognitive and operational levels;

- defining ways to monitor and evaluate learning outcomes;

- creation of conditions for the implementation of the educational program, ensuring the formation of universal competencies; professional development of the teaching staff [3;4;7].

The technological component is provided by the development and implementation of modern technologies necessary to achieve the results of the system of professional training of future teachers. We refer to such prerequisites:

- the presence of motivation for the learning process;
- inclusion of students in active cognitive research and socio-cultural activities.

As the main factor, we define:

- changing the value-semantic goal-setting of learning based on a cognitive activity approach;

- according to which, the requirements for the organization of the educational process are:
- value-semantic modular structuring of the educational program as a way of organizing the educational process;

- designing the content of education on an interdisciplinary integrative basis. For a professional training system focused on a cognitive-activity approach to the learning process, in addition to a set of characteristics inherent in any educational environment, it is necessary to include new, aimed at the formation of activity components.

The activity component provides for the organization of educational activities through information, communication and interactive technologies that give the content of learning an activity-based character;

- ensure the creation of conditions for the value-semantic development of the student's personality;

- the realization of the humanistic potential of learning and communicative communication.

In terms of didactics, we include methodological, methodological and technological security;

- value-semantic modular support of educational programs;
- the ability of students to continuous development and self-development, the development of humanitarian knowledge aimed at the personal social and cognitive needs of the student;

- the orientation of the learning process to the development of experience in practical creative activity, socio-cultural behavior.

The reflexive-evaluative component of the mechanism for the implementation of the cognitive-activity approach should be represented by criteria that allow tracking the levels of formation of universal competencies of future teachers: readiness to navigate the system of universal values; possession of socio-cultural communication skills; readiness for social interaction based on norms accepted in society; the ability and willingness of students to operate knowledge in the process of socio-cultural and professional activities.

The transformation and implementation of acquired knowledge based on a cognitive-activity approach depend on the personal qualities of the student's personality, but the forms and methods of transmitting this information, approaches to implementation in their own life depend not only on the student's personal position, but also on the impact of the educational environment of the educational institution, the professionalism of teachers and socio-cultural factors of society. On the basis of a comprehensive diagnostic methodology, the criteria for the selection of didactic materials for the implementation of a cognitive activity approach in the process of professional training of future teachers are identified and justified: targeted, meaningful, technological, evaluative and effective.

Target criterion: methodological security of strategic and tactical goals of professional training of future teachers based on the conceptual ideas of the cognitive activity approach.

Content criterion: value-semantic modular support
for the design of educational programs in accordance with the objectives, principles and functions of teaching academic disciplines.

Technological criterion: technological and didactic-methodological provision of teaching academic disciplines based on the use of technologies focused on personal and activity structures.

Evaluative and effective criterion: criteria-diagnostic support for the selection of didactic materials for the implementation of the cognitive activity approach contains the structure and content of criteria-diagnostic tools for the effectiveness of the formation of universal competencies in the process of professional training of future teachers: maps of observations and assessments of the formation of universal competencies; diagnostic monitoring of the development of universal competencies of students; expert assessments of the implementation of educational and methodological support. [5, 3-9]

Mastering universal competencies allows you to master generalized methods of action, learn how to solve specific tasks in non-standard situations in a shorter period of study time; and switch to another type of relationship (subject-subject); increase motivation to acquire knowledge based on values and meanings. This approach is aimed at developing the value-semantic sphere of the student and mastering universal ways of activity.

In the experimental work of educational organizations, the following developed criteria for the effectiveness of the formation of universal competencies in the process of implementing a cognitive activity approach are used:

level 1 - the ability to identify the object of study, give its qualitative description, formulate characteristic value properties (universal competencies are not developed);

level 2 - the ability to reproduce the studied material with the required degree of scientific knowledge and value (universal competencies are not sufficiently developed);

level 3 - readiness to use the acquired knowledge as a value in professional activity with the possible use of reference literature, Internet resources (universal competencies are sufficiently developed);

level 4 - the ability to independently perform actions, including in non-standard situations, new conditions, at a new level of value and semantic content (a strong level of development of universal competencies).

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